

CONTROL OF FROG EYE SPOT DISEASE OF TEA IN FIELD

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ABSTRACT

Severe out break of frog eye spot leaf disease caused by the fungal pathogen *Cercospora theae* was noticed for the first time in tea plantations of Anamallais (Valparai, Tamil Nadu). Control of disease using some of the commonly used fungicides in tea plantations was tried. Contact fungicides, (copper oxychloride, copper hydroxide and mancozeb) all at rate of 0.3% were superior to systemic fungicides, carbendazim (0.05%) and hexaconazole (0.28%). Efficient disease control by these fungicides resulted in improved crop protection as evidenced by higher yields in these treatments.

Key words: Tea, *Cercospora theae*, Copper fungicides, Mancozeb

INTRODUCTION

Frog eye spot leaf disease of tea (*Camellia sinensis* (L.) O. Kuntze) caused by the fungal pathogen *Cercospora theae* has a status of minor importance in southern India as it occurs at mild levels in tea nurseries or in mature tea (Baby, 2004). However, during the monsoon months (June - November) of the year 2007, severe outbreaks of the disease have been reported from some of the tea estates in the Anamallais (Valparai, Tamil Nadu) Defoliation of mature leaves and infection on young shoots (crop shoots) was noticed in severely affected tea bushes. This was the first instance of the disease attaining epidemic proportions under conditions of southern India (Ajay *et al.*, 2007). The disease has already been reported to cause devastating damage in tea plantations of Sri Lanka (Petch, 1923). At present, the occasional incidence of frog eye spot disease in tea nurseries is controlled by adopting the same control measures aimed to manage stalk rot disease caused by *Pestalotiopsis theae* (Muraleedharan *et al.*, 2007). Since no work has been done exclusively on the frog eye spot disease control under field conditions, it was sought to investigate the efficacy of certain fungicides, commonly used in tea plantations, to control the disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fungicides tested

Three contact fungicides viz., copper oxychloride (Blitox 50WP) at 0.3%, copper hydroxide (Kocide 101 77WP) at 0.3% and mancozeb (Dithane M45 80WP) at 0.3% and two systemic fungicides, carbendazim (Bavistin 50WP) at 0.05% and hexaconazole (Contaf 5EC) at 0.28% were evaluated.

Field Experiment

The experiment was conducted in the experimental farm (1050 above MSL) at UPASI Tea Research Institute, Valparai in plots planted with Assam tea seedling. Randomised block design was followed with six treatments replicated four times and each replicate had 50 bushes. Fungicides were applied using a knapsack sprayer at an interval of 10 days and untreated plots served as control.

Disease assessment, yield and statistical analysis

Disease assessment was done in the field by quadrat method suggested for grey blight disease of tea (Baby & Sanjay, 2004) with some modifications. Total number of spots in each leaf within the quadrat (1 square foot) was counted and graded on a 0-4 scale, where, grade 0 - leaves without spots, grade 1 - leaves with 1- 20 spots, grade 2- leaves with 20- 40 spots, grade 3 - leaves with 40 - 60 spots and grade 4 leaves with more than 60spots. The disease severity was calculated based on the formula

$$DS = \sum n / (N \times 4) \times 100$$

Where, DS = disease severity, $\sum n$ = sum of individual ratings, N= total number of leaves observed and 4 =highest grade of the scale. In each replicate, quadrat was placed at five randomly selected places and mean value was taken. Disease assessments were made every month and the mean data for the period of six months (June -Nov) is represented. Besides this, green leaf yield was recorded during every harvest and expressed as weight of made tea produced (Kg/ha). The data were subjected to statistical analysis of variance and the significance of difference between the treatments was determined using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Application of fungicides significantly reduced severity of frog eye spot disease compared to untreated control. Among the treatments, disease control achieved with copper hydroxide, copper oxychloride and mancozeb were comparable and significantly superior to carbendazim and hexaconazole (Table 1). Copper fungicides control phytopathogenic fungi by releasing free ionic copper which denatures proteins or enzymes of the pathogen (Nene & Thapliyal, 1993a). Effectiveness of copper formulations in controlling blister blight disease

of tea is already reported (Premkumar *et al.*, 2000). Dithiocarbamate fungicides like mancozeb control pathogenic fungi by various mechanisms like attachment of dithiocarbamate ions to metals bound on proteins or by releasing free radical intermediates which reacts with cellular components of pathogen (Sisler, 1963). Effectiveness of mancozeb sprays at 0.3% in controlling grey blight disease of tea is already known (Sanjay *et al.*, 2008). Even though carbendazim and hexaconazole are effective in controlling other foliar diseases of tea, their performance was comparatively inferior in the present study. This may be due to less sensitivity of the pathogen to these fungicides or may be due to various physical and chemical factors that influence the field performance of fungicides (Nene & Thapliyal, 1993b).

Table 1. Effect of fungicides on frog eye spot disease and yield

Treatments	Disease Severity (%)	Yield (Kg made tea ha ⁻¹)
Copper oxychloride (0.3%)	4.4 a (83.8)	881.1 d
Copper hydroxide (0.3%)	3.9 a (85.6)	885.1 d
Mancozeb (0.3%)	5.0 a (81.5)	877.6 d
Carbendazim (0.05%)	7.8 b (71.2)	863.9 c
Hexaconazole (0.28%)	10.6 c (60.9)	839.3 b
Control	27.1 d	816.2 a

Figures followed by the same letter in a vertical column are not significant different at 5% level by DMRT

Values in parenthesis indicate % protection over untreated control

As in the case of disease control, yield also showed a similar trend. Compared to control, the yield levels were higher in all the fungicide treatments (Table 1). The highest yield was recorded with copper fungicides and mancozeb followed by carbendazim and hexaconazole. The increase in crop yield in fungicide treated plots was due to better protection of crop from the disease. Similar cases of higher yields due to fungicide treatments have already been reported in tea affected by foliar diseases like blister blight (Ajay *et al.*, 2007) and grey blight (Sanjay *et al.*, 2008). Thus the present study revealed the effectiveness of copper fungicides and mancozeb in controlling frog eye spot disease of tea under field conditions.

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REFERENCES

- Ajay, D., Baby, U.I. & Premkumar, R. 2007. Enhancing bioefficacy of fungicides used in tea blister blight control through addition of paraffinic oil. *Journal of Plantation Crops* 35 (1): 33-35
- Ajay, D., Premkumar, R. & Pradeepa, N. 2007. Frog eye spot disease of tea. *News letter of UPASI Tea Research Foundation*. 17 (2): 3
- Baby, U.I. 2004. Diseases of tea. In: *Advances in the Diseases of Plantation Crops and Spices*. Ed. Santha Kumari., P. International Book Distributing Co., Lucknow. pp. 321-343.
- Baby, U.I & Sanjay, R.,. 2004. Economic threshold level of grey blight disease. *News letter of UPASI Tea Research Foundation* 14 (2): 4
- Muraleedharan, N. Hudson, J.B. & Durairaj. 2007. Guidelines of tea culture in southern India. United Planters' Association of Southern India. Connor, India 7: 177
- Nene, Y.L. & Thapliyal, P.N. 1993 a. Fungicides in plant disease control. Oxford & IBH Publishing Company (P) Limited, New Delhi. pp. 121
- Nene, Y.L. & Thapliyal, P.N. 1993 b. Fungicides in plant disease control. Oxford & IBH Publishing Company (P) Limited, New Delhi. pp. 10-15.
- Petch, T. 1923. The diseases of the tea bush. Macmillan and Company Limited, London. pp 36-39
- Premkumar, R., Baby, U.I & Ajay, D. 2000. Efficacy of copper hydroxide in the management of blister blight disease of tea. In: *Proceedings of XIII Symposium on Plantation Crops (PLACROSYM)*. Eds. Muraleedharan, N. and Rajkumar, R. Allied Publishers Limited, Chennai. pp. 415-418
- Sanjay, R., Ponmurugan, P. & Baby, U.I. 2008. Evaluation of fungicides and biocontrol agents against grey blight disease of tea in the field. *Crop Protection*. 27: 689-694
- Sisler, H.D., 1963. Fungitoxic mechanisms. In: *Perspectives of Biochemical Plant Pathology*. Connecticut Agricultural Experimental Station (New Haven) *Bulletin*. 663:116-136